

Improving Social Media Information Extraction using Multitask Multidataset Learning

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Information extraction (IE) from text data is often a first step conducting social media research [3, 9, 10]. Text based information extraction usually deals with identifying named entities, sentiment, topics, in a given piece of text. However, this information extraction process when applied to social media data offers several challenges because of the noisy text [1], varying guidelines[7], rapidly increasing vocabulary [6], semantic and syntactic drift in language usage [5, 6], and short text context [4–6, 13]. This problem is exacerbated by the lack of consistently annotated large scale social media corpora. Training a single machine learning model for each IE task and social media dataset can be cumbersome and likely to overfit to the trends in the dataset. In this work, we investigate the usage of multi-task learning [2, 8, 11, 12] to overcome the data sparsity issue as well as to build more robust and generalizable models. Our work extends the application of multi-task learning at large scale to social media datasets including classification and sequence tagging tasks. We utilize the concept of multi-dataset multi-task learning (see 1), which effectively leverages datasets annotated with varying annotation guidelines (**multi-dataset mode**) across multiple tasks (**multi-task mode**). We evaluate this approach on three text classification tasks as well as four sequence tagging tasks. The text classification tasks include sentiment classification, abusive content identification, and uncertainty identification. The sequence tagging tasks include part-of-speech (PoS) tagging, phrase chunking, named entity recognition (NER), and supersense (CCG) tagging. We achieve state of the art results (88% micro-f1 on sentiment, 80-84% micro-f1 on abusive, and 39-85% micro-f1 on uncertainty tasks, as well as 90% accuracy on POS tagging, 50-89% micro-f1 on NER, 88% micro-f1 on chunking, and 42-59% micro-f1 on supersense tagging) on many of the included test datasets using the proposed multi-task multi-dataset models. This allows us to have a single model which can perform at par or better than individually trained models for a variety of social media IE tasks. The benefit of using this approach is reduced model deployment and inference cost. Finally, we investigate the label embeddings in our multi-task model and identify that these embeddings encode task and label similarity information without explicitly including this information.

In the last layer of the model, the score for each label is computed by taking a dot product of the input token representation with the vector for each of the labels. This results in a vector representation being learned for each label. We can investigate the space of these label representations to know the similarity of two labels. We use the multi-task model for our analysis as this model is one of the most consistent models in across all evaluation datasets.

Figure 1: Possible model configurations.

UMAP projection of classification labels is shown in figure 2. We observe that labels which represent similar meaning across different datasets cluster together in this representation space. Some interesting observations are the closeness of neutral, uncertain, none, normal, and not_sarcasm. Each of these classes represents the base class of their dataset, and we observe that they are quite similar in their representation space. Similarly, negative, abusive, hateful, sexism, and racism are clustered together compared to positive. This result shows that our model is learning relationship between the labels, which can be utilized for model verification.

Figure 2: UMAP representation for classification embeddings of multi-task model

Our contributions can be summarized as follows: (1) We introduce the first large scale MDMT meta-corpus for social media IE. (2) We introduce MDMT models for efficient and more accurate IE on social media text. (3) We investigate the internal encoding of these MDMT models via label embeddings. (4) We publicly release our pre-trained models and tools at <https://socialmediaie.github.io>

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